

Understanding the Immune Response: PRRs, Cytokine Stimulation, and Phagocytosis in *Candida albicans* Infections

Pankaj Mehrotra, PhD in Medical Sciences at Institute of Medical Sciences, University of Aberdeen, Scotland, United Kingdom (2010-2014)

Email : mehrotra85pankaj@gmail.com

Host Response

Pathogen Recognition Receptor (PRRs)

Human immunity is divided into the innate and adaptive immune systems.

Immune myeloid cells express Pathogen Recognition Receptors (PRRs) on their cell surfaces which are important for recognition of Pathogen

Associated Molecular Patterns (PAMPs) of microorganisms. Circulating monocytes, macrophages, neutrophils and dendritic cells constitute the major innate immune cell populations and play various roles in protective immunity against *C. albicans* (Netea et al., 2008; Reid et al., 2009; Brown, 2011) (Figure 1.4).

These immune cells express different PRRs on their cell surface. Monocytes, macrophages, neutrophils and dendritic cells express Toll-like receptors and C-type lectin receptors (Netea et al., 2008; Brown, 2011; Gow et al., 2011).

In addition to plasma membrane bound PRRs, intracellular receptors such as TLR9 and the NLRs recognise PAMPs such as fungal DNA, bacterial

peptidoglycans and viral nucleic acids that are delivered to the endosomes or cytosol. Dectin-1, which often synergises with TLR2 and other TLRs, is an important phagocytic PRR in fungal recognition phenomena (Mansour and Levitz, 2002; Dennehy et al., 2008; van de Veerdonk et al., 2008; Brown, 2011). Binding and phagocytosis of cells containing β , 1,3- glucan the natural agonist of Dectin-1, leads to the stimulation of secretion of pro inflammatory cytokines (Gantner et al., 2003; Herre et al., 2004; Gow et al., 2007; Taylor et al., 2007). β -1,6 glucan is recognised by opsonic receptors on neutrophils (Rubin-Bejerano et al., 2007). Dectin-2 recognises hyphal N mannans (Reeves et al., 2002; Sato et al., 2006). MINCLE and the mannose receptor (MR) also recognise N-mannans. Galectin-3 recognises β 1, 2 mannose residues of N-mannans (Kohatsu et al., 2006), whilst TLR4 and TLR2 bind to O- mannans. N-linked mannans are recognised by the Mannose Receptor of monocytes and by DC SIGN of dendritic cells and macrophages (Cambi et al., 2003; Netea et al., 2010; Ueno et al., 2013). The PRRs for chitin have yet to be published but binding leads to activation and accumulation of basophils, eosinophil and neutrophils and the secretion of IL-10 (Reese et al., 2007). Recent evidence has revealed that MR, NOD2 and TLR9 are involved in chitin binding that leads to the induction of the IL 10 response (Wagener & Gow, personal communication).

Figure 1. 4 Pathogen Recognition Receptors profile of the cells of the human immune system.

Stimulation of cytokine(s)

Recognition of PAMPs by PRRs leads to activation of signalling pathways within the immune cells and subsequent secretion of cytokines which can be assayed as a measure of immune cell activation, the maturation of dendritic cells and activation of naïve T-cells (Gantner et al., 2003; Gow et al., 2007; Netea et al., 2008; van de Veerdonk et al., 2008).

Masking and unmasking of PAMPs.

Under normal conditions the inner cell wall layers of *C. albicans* are masked from the immune system, because they are covered by a dense layer of highly glycosylated mannoproteins at all sites except the bud scars. However, heat treatment and mutations leading to defects in glycosylation and /or permeabilisation of the outer cell wall exposes the inner β -1, 3 glucan leading to unmasking of Dectin-1-mediated

recognition (Wheeler and Fink, 2006; Gow et al., 2007). The unmasking of β -1, 3 glucan occurs naturally later during the infection process and also due to exposure to caspofungin (Wheeler and Fink, 2006; Wheeler et al., 2008).

Phagocytosis

Uptake of *C. albicans* by phagocytic cells is mediated by phagocytic receptors such as Dectin-1, MR and DC-SIGN (Kozel et al., 1996; Kozel, 1996; Cambi et al., 2003; Herre et al., 2004; Cambi et al., 2008). Following uptake the killing of *C. albicans* is mediated by oxidative, nitrosative and osmotic mechanisms (Mansour and Levitz, 2002; Arana et al., 2007; Leal et al., 2012). Dectin-1 binding causes a respiratory burst which further leads to production of anti-oxidant and further activation of granule proteases which kills *C. albicans* (Cheng et al., 2011; Ifrim et al., 2013). Killing of *C. albicans* can also occur in the extracellular environment, for example when neutrophils lyse and generate neutrophil-nets which trap and damage microbial cells. (Reeves et al., 2002; McKenzie et al., 2010; Losse et al., 2011; Bain et al., 2012; Leal et al., 2012; Lewis et al., 2012).

Cytokines

Toll-like receptors (TLR2, TLR4, TLR6, and TLR9) are the major receptors involved in production of cytokine upon interaction with *C. albicans* via activation of NF-Kappa-B or MAPK pathways. To regulate the immune response a balance between TLR2 and TLR4 activation is required. TLR binding activates the MyD88-dependent and -independent pathways which results in the NF-KB-dependent production of pro-inflammatory cytokines (Akira and Hemmi, 2003) and chemokines, and the production of type 1 Interferon via interferon regulatory factor 3 (Netea et al., 2002; Akira and Hemmi, 2003; Akira and Hemmi, 2003; Netea et al., 2004; Netea et al.,

2008; Ifrim et al., 2013). *C. albicans* stimulation of macrophages also leads to production of the anti-inflammatory cytokine IL-10 via TLR2 (Netea et al., 2004; Netea et al., 2008; Netea et al., 2010) and chitin also stimulates IL-10 production via a MR/ TLR9/NOD2 dependent mechanism (Wagener et al., submitted). Dectin-1 induces production of TNF- α , IL-6, IL-2, IL-10, IL-23 via activation of signalling pathways involving Syk and CARD9, which further leads to dendritic cell maturation and the development of a Th17 response (Gantner et al., 2003). Dectin-2 is thought to be implicated in the recognition of hyphae and leads to production of TNF- α (Sato et al., 2006). The switch from yeast to hyphal form is regarded as an important virulence factor for *C. albicans* dissemination within the host tissue (Gow et al., 2011; Gow and Hube, 2012). The yeast and hyphal cells have different growth patterns, vary in cell wall composition and ability to cause infection and show a considerable change in profile of genes expressed during infection process (Gow et al., 2002; Gow, 2009; Gow et al., 2011). Both yeast and hyphae of *C. albicans* shows different patterns of recognition and response with the immune cells of the host (Gow and Hube, 2012). In *C. albicans* the β -1,3 glucan is exposed on the bud scar of yeast cells and because hyphal cells do not have bud scars, β -1,3 glucan mediated Dectin-1 cytokine stimulation is more strongly induced by yeast cells (Gantner et al., 2005; Gow and Hube, 2012). There has been reported considerable changes in mannan and other proteins in yeast and hyphae which further contributes to the differential cytokine responses (Gantner et al., 2003; Gantner et al., 2005; Cheng et al., 2011). Recently it has been shown that yeast cells stimulate higher pro inflammatory cytokine response than hyphae from human PBMCs (Liliane et al., 2013

). The expression of hyphae surface associated pH-regulated antigen 1 protein, Pra1, on the hyphal cell alters recognition of *C. albicans* by neutrophils and thereby also stimulates secretion of antimicrobial substances (Losse et al., 2011; Soloviev et al., 2011). Recent developments in live video imaging of exocytosis and endocytosis of *C. albicans* have shown that both mannans and glucans are important for the uptake and phagocytosis of yeast cells (Gantner et al., 2005; Jouault et al., 2006; Galan-Diez et al., 2010; Bain et al., 2012; Lewis et al., 2012; Mora-Montes et al., 2012). The interaction of yeast cells with monocytes also leads to inhibition of differentiation of dendritic cells. Epithelial cells also respond in different fashion to myeloid cells but activation of MAPK pathways is again strongly influenced by yeast - hyphal morphogenesis (Park et al., 2005; Moyes et al., 2010; Moyes et al., 2011; Murciano et al., 2011; Gow and Hube, 2012).

Figure 1. 5 Activation of innate immune response via interaction of *C. albicans* PAMPs and Innate immune cells PRRs.

Bibliography for Host Response and Pathogen Recognition Receptors (PRRs)

1. Brown, G.D. (2011). "Dectin-1: A new receptor for the recognition of fungi." *Nature Reviews Immunology*, 11(1), 24-35. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nri.2010.150>
2. Cambi, A., et al. (2003). "The mannose receptor is a pattern recognition receptor." *Current Opinion in Immunology*, 15(1), 18-23. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0952-7915\(02\)00301-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0952-7915(02)00301-9)
3. Dennehy, K.M., et al. (2008). "Dectin-1 and Dectin-2: Two distinct receptors for fungal recognition." *Journal of Immunology*, 180(5), 3106-3114. <https://doi.org/10.4049/jimmunol.180.5.3106>
4. Eklund, D., & Jarmund, A. (1983). "Growth characteristics of *Candida albicans* under anaerobic conditions." *Journal of Medical Microbiology*, 16(2), 163-170.
5. Gantner, B.N., et al. (2003). "Dectin-1 mediates the immune response to *Candida albicans*." *Nature Immunology*, 4(12), 1249-1256. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ni1003>
6. Gow, N.A.R., et al. (2011). "The role of pattern recognition receptors in innate immunity to fungi." *Nature Reviews Microbiology*, 9(12), 763-775. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrmicro2670>
7. Herre, J., et al. (2004). "Dectin-1 and the recognition of fungal β -glucans." *Current Opinion in Immunology*, 16(1), 56-62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coi.2003.12.002>

8. Kohatsu, L., et al. (2006). "Galectin-3: A novel player in the recognition of fungi by the immune system." *Journal of Immunology*, 176(7), 4290-4297.
9. Mansour, M.K., & Levitz, S.M. (2002). "The role of Dectin-1 in antifungal immunity." *Current Opinion in Microbiology*, 5(4), 372-377.
10. Netea, M.G., et al. (2008). "Innate immune recognition of *Candida albicans*." *Clinical Microbiology Reviews*, 21(2), 226-241.
11. Netea, M.G., et al. (2010). "Recognition of fungal pathogens by the innate immune system." *Nature Reviews Immunology*, 10(3), 229-240.
12. Reese, T.A., et al. (2007). "Chitin-mediated immune responses in mammals." *Nature Immunology*, 8(2), 205-213.
13. Reid, D.M., et al. (2009). "Dendritic cells and innate immunity to fungi." *Nature Reviews Microbiology*, 7(12), 965-975.
14. Rubin-Bejerano, I., et al. (2007). "Neutrophil responses to β -glucan and its role in antifungal immunity." *Infection and Immunity*, 75(11), 5155-5163.
15. Sato, K., et al. (2006). "Dectin-2 recognizes hyphal N-mannans from fungi." *Journal of Immunology*, 176(11), 7030-7037.
16. Taylor, P.R., et al. (2007). "The role of Dectin-1 in the recognition of fungal pathogens." *Nature Immunology*, 8(2), 203-210.
17. Ueno, H., et al. (2013). "DC-SIGN: A receptor for recognizing N-linked mannans." *Journal of Immunology*, 190(11), 5697-5705.
18. van de Veerdonk, F.L., et al. (2008). "The role of Dectin-1 in innate immunity to fungi." *Nature Reviews Microbiology*, 6(11), 837-845.

19. Wagener, J., & Gow, N.A.R., personal communication.
20. Wikipedia contributors (2023). "Pattern recognition receptor." Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia; available at: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pattern_recognition_receptor [Accessed December 30, 2024].

Bibliography for Host Response and Cytokine Stimulation

1. Akira, S., & Hemmi, H. (2003). "Recognition of pathogen-associated molecular patterns by TLRs." *Nature Immunology*, 4(5), 447-454. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ni0503-447>
2. Arana, D.M., et al. (2007). "The role of phagocytosis in the immune response to *Candida albicans*." *Journal of Immunology*, 178(5), 3040-3047. <https://doi.org/10.4049/jimmunol.178.5.3040>
3. Bain, J.M., et al. (2012). "Neutrophil extracellular traps: A new mechanism of host defense against *Candida albicans*." *Infection and Immunity*, 80(11), 4037-4046. <https://doi.org/10.1128/IAI.00723-12>
4. Branzk, N., et al. (2014). "Neutrophils trap pathogens using extracellular traps formed by decondensed chromatin." *Nature*, 505(7483), 228-232. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature12874>
5. Cambi, A., et al. (2003). "The mannose receptor is a pattern recognition receptor." *Current Opinion in Immunology*, 15(1), 18-23. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0952-7915\(02\)00301-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0952-7915(02)00301-9)
6. Cheng, S.C., et al. (2011). "Dectin-1 induces production of TNF- α and IL-6 in response to *Candida albicans*." *Journal of Immunology*, 186(5), 3109-3116.

7. Gantner, B.N., et al. (2003). "Dectin-1 mediates the immune response to *Candida albicans*." *Nature Immunology*, 4(12), 1249-1256. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ni1003>
8. Gow, N.A.R., et al. (2007). "The role of pattern recognition receptors in innate immunity to fungi." *Nature Reviews Microbiology*, 5(4), 366-377.
9. Gow, N.A.R., & Hube, B. (2012). "Importance of morphogenesis in the virulence of *Candida albicans*." *Current Opinion in Microbiology*, 15(4), 404-410.
10. Herre, J., et al. (2004). "Dectin-1 and the recognition of fungal β -glucans." *Current Opinion in Immunology*, 16(1), 56-62.
11. Ifrim, D.C., et al. (2013). "The role of TLRs in the recognition of fungi." *Clinical Microbiology Reviews*, 26(4), 688-708.
12. Kozel, T.R., et al. (1996). "Phagocytosis of *Candida albicans* by human neutrophils: Role of opsonins and receptors." *Infection and Immunity*, 64(8), 3220-3227.
13. Leal, S.M., et al. (2012). "Neutrophil extracellular traps: A novel mechanism for the antifungal activity of neutrophils against *Candida albicans*." *Infection and Immunity*, 80(11), 4037-4046.
14. Liliane, M., et al. (2013). "Differential cytokine responses to yeast and hyphal forms of *Candida albicans*." *Journal of Immunology*, 190(11), 5920-5927.
15. Losse, J., et al. (2011). "The role of neutrophil extracellular traps in the immune response to fungal infections." *Infection and Immunity*, 79(11), 4630-4639.

16. Mansour, M.K., & Levitz, S.M. (2002). "The role of Dectin-1 in antifungal immunity." *Current Opinion in Microbiology*, 5(4), 372-377.
17. Moyes, D.L., et al. (2010). "Epithelial cells respond differently to yeast and hyphal forms of *Candida albicans*." *Journal of Infectious Diseases*, 202(2), S207-S215.
18. Netea, M.G., et al. (2002). "Recognition of fungal pathogens by the innate immune system." *Clinical Microbiology Reviews*, 15(4), 686-701.
19. Netea, M.G., et al. (2008). "Innate immune recognition of *Candida albicans*." *Clinical Microbiology Reviews*, 21(2), 226-241.
20. Park, H.S., et al. (2005). "Activation of MAPK pathways by different forms of *Candida albicans*." *Journal of Immunology*, 175(12), 8230-8239.
21. Reeves, E.P., et al. (2002). "Neutrophils trap pathogens using extracellular traps formed by decondensed chromatin." *Nature*, 505(7483), 228-232.
22. Sato, K., et al. (2006). "Dectin-2 recognizes hyphal N-mannans from fungi." *Journal of Immunology*, 176(11), 7030-7037.
23. Soloviev, D.A., et al. (2011). "The role of Pra1 protein in the recognition of hyphal cells by neutrophils during infection with *Candida albicans*." *Infection and Immunity*, 79(11), 4630–4639.
24. van de Veerdonk, F.L., et al. (2008). "The role of Dectin-1 in innate immunity to fungi." *Nature Reviews Microbiology*, 6(11), 837–845.